

turntable at 25 ml/pot at 5 days after transplanting. Each treatment was replicated twice. The sprayed plants were allowed to dry for 1 hour. Twenty brachypterous BPH females in the 1st experiment and 20 5th-instar GLH nymphs in the 2d, were caged on treated plants with a glass tube covered with muslin. The exposure periods were 1, 2, 4, and 6 hours for BPH and 0.5, 1, 2, and 3 hours for GLH. Mortality was recorded after the exposure periods. Moribund insects were treated as dead. For mortality in the control, the corrected percentage of mortality in the treatment was calculated by Abbott's

LT₅₀ and LT₉₀ values of pesticides against the brown planthopper and green leafhopper. Bhopal, M.P., India.

Pesticide	Conc (% active ingredient)	Values (h)			
		Brown planthopper		Green leafhopper	
		LT ₅₀	LT ₉₀	LT ₅₀	LT ₉₀
Control	0	—	—	—	—
Methyl parathion	0.025	3.5	5.0	1.6	2.0
Quinalphos	0.025	2.4	5.0	1.5	2.2
Phosphamidon	0.025	2.6	4.0	1.5	2.4
Carbaryl	0.05	2.0	3.0	1.25	1.8
BPMC	0.05	< 1.0	1.0	0.8	1.1
BPMC + carbaryl (1:1)	0.05	1.1	1.8	0.6	0.9
Landrin	0.05	2.0	3.0	1.5	2.5

formula and plotted on log-probit paper against time in hours; graphical Lethal Time (LT₅₀) and Lethal Time 90 (LT₉₀)

were calculated for the different insecticides (see table). ■

Leaf folder control through interference in chitin biosynthesis

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The effect on larvae of the leaf folder *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis* Guenee of a new insecticide Dimilin (R)—with a unique mode of action on insects was studied. Dimilin (diflubenzuron) interferes with chitin biosynthesis and deposition in the insect cuticle. Interference in chitin deposition in the insect exoskeleton leads to inhibition of molting.

Potted TN1 rice plants were sprayed with 200 ppm Dimilin with a hand atomizer. When the spray fluid dried up, final-instar larvae of the leaf folder were released on plants confined in cylindrical

Morphogenetic changes in leaf folder larvae that fed on Dimilin®-treated rice leaves. A: normal pupae; B: pupae with deformed proboscis; C & D: larval-pupal mosaics. Tamil Nadu, India.

polyester cages. The larvae which fed on Dimilin-treated plants formed silken webs, but were unable to molt and develop into pupae (see figure). The insecticide caused deformities: pupae with deformed proboscis and larval-pupal mosaics. The pupal deformities are evidently due to interference in chitin

deposition. In all the 5 replications of 10 larvae each, 80% of the test insects were deformed. The result suggests that Dimilin—a new generation of insecticide—has the potential to control the rice leaf folder through physiological inhibition of chitin deposition. ■

Irrigation and water management

Effect of irrigation regimes on agronomic characters of rice

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The effects of different irrigation regimes on agronomic traits of the semidwarf rice variety Cauvery were studied in a greenhouse trial. Continuous flooding

was the superior irrigation regime in its influence on grain yield and nutrient recovery, but it did not improve the harvest index. Yield and nutrient recovery performance was poor in rice plants grown under continuous saturated conditions. Flooding at the reproductive stage was found to increase yield, nutrient recovery, and harvest index more

than flooding at the vegetative stage.

Nutrient recovery was closely associated with yield but harvest index was an independent trait and differed from yield trends. Harvest index decreased successively in the following order of irrigation regime: I₂, I₁, I₄, I₃ (see table). The highest harvest index in treatment I₂ was probably because of proper equi-

Effect of different irrigation regimes on some agronomic characteristics of indica rice, Varanasi, India.

Treatment	Grain yield ^a (g/hill)	Harvest index ^a (%)	Relative efficiency of nutrient recovery (%)	
			Nitrogen	Phosphorus
I ₁ Continuous saturation at maximum water-holding capacity	20.3 d	52 b	100	100
I ₂ Saturation during vegetative + flooding during reproductive stage	29.4 b	58 a	147	155
I ₃ Flooding during vegetative stage + saturation during reproductive stage	23.4 c	43 d	124	142
I ₄ Continuous flooding (5 cm depth)	32.9 a	46 c	155	113
Significance	*	*	–	–
C.D. at 5% level	2.13	2.61		

^aMean values with the same letter do not differ significantly.

butrium between the growth rates in the vegetative and reproductive stages. But although flooding at the vegetative stage increased the rice plant's vegetation

appreciably, saturation during the development of reproductive organs caused a setback (see table). ■

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Soil and crop management

Blue-green algae in deepwater rice in Mali, West Africa

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Epiphytic algae on rice may contribute to the fertility of paddy soils and may be important where fertilizers are not used. Their presence in deepwater rice has been reported in Bangladesh. This

article reports the presence of blue-green algae (BGA) in deepwater rice in Africa.

Stem sections of variety Mogo, *Oryza glaberrima*, including nodal roots and leaf sheaths, were removed from a field of deepwater rice near Mopti, Mali, on 10 October 1978. The water was 165 cm deep. The stem sections were preserved in 2% formalin (39% formaldehyde).

The algae from both the sedimented samples and various parts of the rice plant were examined. The former served as a check for the occurrence and

relative abundance of the algae in the latter's habitat. The algae were observed directly through a compound microscope. Temporary mounts were prepared in lactophenol blue from a 2- to 3-mm² pieces of leaf sheaths and leaf blades, and from pieces of nodal roots about 1-2 mm long. The cover slips were later sealed with melted paraffin and kept in the herbarium of the UPLB.

Twenty-six species of algae were identified from the material. The table lists the BGA and indicates their relative abundance. BGA constituted the greatest algal bulk in the sample. Of the eight species of BGA identified, seven are nitrogen fixers: *Anabaena torulosa*, *A. vaginicola*, *Cylindrospermum licheniforme*, *Gloeocapsa quaternata*, *Gloeotrichia natans*, *Hapalosiphon stuhlmanii*, and *Nostoc* sp.

The chlorophytes were well represented (13 species) but only *Bulbochaete* sp. and *Oedogonium* sp. were present in significant numbers. Five species of euglenophytes and diatoms occurred in low numbers. ■

Blue-green algae observed on deepwater rice Mogo, in Mopti, Mali, West Africa.

Species	Relative abundance ^a		
	Leaf/ leaf sheath	Nodal roots	Sediment
<i>Anabaena torulosa</i> (Carm.) Lag.			++++
<i>A. vaginicola</i> Fritsch et Rich	+++	+++	+++
<i>Chroococcus limneticus</i> Lemm.	++	++	++
<i>Cylindrospermum licheniforme</i> (Bory) Kuetz.	+++	++	++
<i>Gloeocapsa quaternata</i> (Breb.) Kuetz.	+		+
<i>Gloeotrichia natans</i> (Hedw.) Rabh.	++++	+++	++++
<i>Hapalosiphon stuhlmanii</i> Hieron.	++++	+++	++++
<i>Nostoc</i> sp.	++++		++

^a++++ = abundant, +++ = moderate, ++ = rare, + = very rare.